

Die Suche nach dem kreiselnden Kühlgerät - Ideenkarten -

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Ideenkarten

Ein Mittel zur Katalogisierung und Clustering von gesammelten Ideen rund um das Kühlen von Lebensmitteln

Auf der Suche nach dem kreiselnden Kühlgerät sind zahlreiche Ideen entstanden. Diese sind in den Workshops, Kursen, Projekttreffen und Recherchen entstanden. Aus ihnen sind insgesamt 48 Ideenkarten entstanden. Die Vorderseite zeigt jeweils eine Grafik und eine kurze Beschreibung, die dabei helfen, die Idee schnell erfassen zu können. Auf der Rückseite sind Adressaten, Anknüpfungspunkte, Vorteile, Nachteile und einige Notizen zu finden. Ähnlich wie beim Sustainable Mobility Kit (Gallico & Bazilevich, 2020) sollen die Karten zum gemeinsamen Spielen und Experimentieren anregen. Wobei im vorliegenden Fall die Karten selbst ergänzt und bearbeitet werden sollen.

Connected Cooling

A large refrigerator is more efficient than two small ones. In this concept, one large refrigerator is used across two apartments. A wall break-through between apartments would be conceivable here.

Today — 2025 — 2035 — 2045 — 2055 — 2065 — Future

Address

- Efficiency
- Reduce (Energy and Components)
- Architects, Manufacturers

Pro

- Low energy consumption.
- Only one compressor needed.

Contra

- Architectural solution connected with high effort and costs.
- Low flexibility.

Notes

001

Cooling Door

The refrigerator is reduced to its door. Therefore the cooling technology is inside of it and can be mounted on an insulated box or a wall niche.

Today — 2025 — 2035 — 2045 — 2055 — 2065 — Future

Address

- Consistency
- Recycle, Reduce, Remanufacture
- Recycler, User, Manufacturer

Pro

- Cooling door can be easily repaired, exchanged or upgraded.
- Heat can be released directly into the room.

Contra

- Door might get thick and heavy.

Notes

002

Cool Chain Delivery

Delivery services are able to deliver food directly into the customers refrigerator. The domestic fridge freezer combination is accessible for the supplier.

Address

- Consistency
- Reduce
- Manufacturer, Architects, Food Industry

Pro

- Reductions of food packaging might be possible.

Contra

- Difficult in realisation.

Notes

003

Rent a Fridge

A rental fridge is a solution for people, whose living conditions are often in a state of change. In each living situation the right cooling unit could be provided.

Address

- Sufficiency
- Reuse
- Manufacturer, User, Recycler

Pro

- Fridges are getting upgraded and reused.
- Old fridges would be collected by the rental company.

Contra

- Reboundeffect: a more frequent exchange of fridges.

Notes

004

Window Sill Cooling

An evaporative refrigerator for the window sill, not much bigger than a flower pot, would keep the essential food in the household fresh.

Address

- Efficiency / Sufficiency
- Reduce
- User

Pro

- No energy is needed for the cooling of food.
- Less food is disposed as it is easier to keep track of it.

Contra

- Not enough cooling space.
- Not always cold enough.

Notes

<https://goexplorer.org/clay-fridge-cools-through-evaporation/>

005

Low-Tech Fridge Extension

The actual fridge volume can be temporarily extended by the usage of an isolated storage module, which is cooled by low-tech cool packs. Therefore the actual fridge size could be reduced.

Address

- Efficiency, Sufficiency
- Reduce
- User

Pro

- Temporary extension of cooling volume.
- Reduction of electrically operated cooling volume.

Contra

- Usage of low-tech fridge extension has to be planned (Preparation of cool packs).

Notes

006

A Central Food Storage

The fridge is the central food storage of the household and is enabling appropriate storage space for all groceries - cooled and not cooled.

Address

- Sufficiency
- Reduce (Food waste, food in the fridge)
- User

Pro

- Clearly structured storage of food.

Contra

- The central food storage might not fit into standard kitchen designs.

Notes

007

Multiple Openings

Smaller and more fridge opening possibilities (doors, drawers ect.) are enabling less cooling loss when opened.

Address

- Efficiency
- Reduce (Energy)
- User

Pro

- Less loss of cold air.

Contra

- More resources in production.
- Loss of interior space.

Notes

008

Transparency of the Outside

A transparent appearance is enabling transparency in the usage. The user can locate needed items before opening the door, to reduce the cooling loss. Furthermore food waste might be reduced as the fridge content is more present.

Address

- Efficiency
- Reduce (Energy?)
- User

Pro

- Better overview of food.
- Locate items before opening the door.

Contra

- A transparent outside is less energy efficient and enables loss of cold air.

Notes

009

Transparency of the Inside

A transparent order system in the inside of the fridge (boxes, visual labelling etc.) can support a more efficient usage of the cooling volume and can prevent from long searches for specific items.

Address

- Efficiency
-
- User (knowledge transfer)

Pro

- Better and more efficient order system.
- Cooling zones are correctly used.

Contra

- Might not have enough impact.

Notes

010

Modular Interior

The inner structure of the fridge is modular and can be adjusted to the storage and diet preferences of the user.

Address

- Sufficiency
- Reuse, Reduce
- User

Pro

- Fridge lifetime might be extended.
- A individual System of order can be created.

Contra

- Might not have enough impact.

Notes

011

Modular Exterior

The exterior appearance and arrangement of the fridge is modular. If the design is not fitting anymore it can be easily adapted to the new preferences of the user.

Address

- Sufficiency
- Reuse, Reduce
- User

Pro

- Fridge lifetime might be extended.
- Fridge can adapt to changes of Different phases of life

Contra

- Separated cooling units and therefore more resources are needed.

Notes

012

Modular Technology

The technology part of the fridge is modular and therefore it can be easily repaired, it can be upgraded or exchanged.

Address

- Sufficiency
- Reduce, Reuse, Recycle
- Manufacturer, User, Recycler

Pro

- Repair, exchange and upgrade are more easy.

Contra

- Possibility of realisation?

Notes

013

Community Fridge

Communally used fridges in residential buildings can facilitate cooling space for more than just one household.

Address

- Sufficiency
- Reduce (number of fridges)
- Architects, Manufacturer, User

Pro

- Less private fridges, less energy consumption.

Contra

- Inconvenient in every day life.

Notes

014

Solar Fridge

The fridge is being powered by solar energy when it is possible.

Address

- Efficiency, Consistency
- Reduce
- Manufacturer, User

Pro

- Solar power = renewable energy.
- Hot weather = low temperature

Contra

- What happens if the sun is not shining?
- Solarpanel must be located outside.

Notes

<https://www.liebherr.com/de/int/aktuelles/stories/solarkuehlschrank/die-kaelte-die-von-der-sonne-kam.html> (hat sich nicht verkauft)

015

Fridge with a Handle

A fridge with an integrated handle can make the transport, return to and handling at the recycler / refurbishment company more easy.

Address

- Consistency
- Recycle, Reuse
- Recycler, trader, user

Pro

- More easy transport/handling of the fridge.

Contra

- Just a handle is not guaranteeing that the fridge is being transported to the recycler.

Notes

016

Exterior Cooling

Outdoor temperatures are being used to cool groceries. Cold air can be redirected to the inside of the fridge to reduce the energy usage. Also there might be outside storage systems that are enabling the food storage on the balcony / garden.

Address

- Consistency
- Reduce (Energy)
- User, architect, manufacturer

Pro

- Reduction of energy consumption in colder seasons.

Contra

- Elaborate construction measures might be needed.

Notes

017

Recycling Fridge

This fridge is consisting at least out of 60 % of recycling materials. Furthermore recycling of the fridge components at the end of its lifetime is made possible.

Address

- Consistency
- Recycle
- Manufacturer, Recycler

Pro

- Usage of secondary material instead of primary material.

Contra

- The material quality is being reduced through each cycle (Downwards Spiral).

Notes

018

Alternative Isolation Materials

Alternative and natural materials as for example fungus are being used as an isolation. These materials need to be eco-friendly or recyclable.

Address

- Consistency
- Recycle
- Manufacturer

Pro

- These materials might be recyclable or/and renewable.
- Less harmful for the environment.

Contra

- Heat insulation might be less Effective.
- Production process would need to be changed.

Notes

019

Life without Fridge

Cooled food delivery hubs are available in neighbourhoods. Purchasing behavior of people has changed. Regularly fresh food deliveries can be picked up at the hub. The shopping experience at a supermarket is getting redundant.

Address

- Sufficiency
- Reduce
- User

Pro

- Less personal fridges, less energy Consumption.

Contra

- Reboundeffects of regular food deliveries?
- Shopping experience vs. online shopping?

Notes

020

Earth Refrigerator

An earth refrigerator is used to keeping groceries cool without needing any power supply.

Today → 2025 | 2035 | 2045 | 2055 | 2065 **Future**

Address

- Consistency
- Reduce
- Architects/Manufacturer, User

Pro

- Less energy consumption.

Contra

- Not possible without a garden and therefore only possible for certain people (> impact?).
- Inconvenient as it is outside of the flat.

Notes

021

Utilization of Residual Heat

The heat that derives through the backwall of the fridge is being reused.

Today → 2025 | 2035 | 2045 | 2055 | 2065 **Future**

Address

- Consistency
- User

Pro

- The residual heat is not wasted.

Contra

- Inconvenient as the heat is created at the backwall of the fridge.

Notes

022

Renewable Film in the Inner Wall

After a period of usage, the fridge interior is equipped with a new film. Alternative: new exchangeable inner container

Address

- Sufficiency
- Reuse
- User / Service Provider

Pro

- Possibility of recreate the condition of the fridge to make reuse more attractive.

Contra

- Practicability?
- Bacteria under the layers

Notes

023

Fridge Deposit

A deposit is paid when a refrigerator is purchased. It is paid back when the appliance is returned correctly.

Address

- Consistency
- Recycle
- Manufacturer, Dealer

Pro

- More fridges might be returned in order to be recycled.

Contra

- Who gets the deposit and who is paying it back? Responsibilities Need to be discussed.

Notes

024

Panel Construction

The outer shell of the fridge is constructed out of modular metal sheet material.

Address

- Sufficiency
- Reuse, Remanufacture, Recycle
- Manufacturer, User, Recycler

Pro

- Simplicity of construction.
- More easy to reuse.
- More easy to recycle.

Contra

Notes

025

Directional Fridge

The fridge has a clear direction to make the extraction of the coolant more easy.

Address

- Efficiency
- Recycle
- Recycler

Pro

- less coolant residues in the compressor

Contra

-

Notes

additional standard holder for removing the coolant

026

Foodsharing Fridge

Community fridges are placed in neighbourhoods especially for food sharing reasons.

Address

- Sufficiency
- Reuse (Food:)
- User

Pro

- Less food waste.
- Shared food.

Contra

- Impact?

Notes

027

House Insulation

The isolation layer is added to the inner fridge shell, similar to the process of insulating a house.

Address

- Consistency
- Recycle
- Manufacturer, Recycler

Pro

- Simplicity of construction is making recycling more easy.

Contra

- Isolation = Outside layer of fridge?

Notes

- Is the base an naked fridge?

028

Clever Connector

A clever connector is used to join the exterior of the fridge. This can be combined with modular exterior panels. Therefore the fridge can be disassembled more easy.

Address

- Consistency
- Recycle, Reuse
- Manufacturer, Recycler

Pro

- The construction of the fridge is allowing repair and refurbishment.
- Parts can be separated more easy.

Contra

- Which parts would be joined by the connector?

Notes

- "IKEA" Fridge?

029

Door-Closing / Opening

The fridge door is closing automatically after being opened to prevent it from being left open. Furthermore the interaction of the opening of the door can be reconsidered.

Address

- Efficiency
- Reduce (Energy)
- User, Manufacturer

Pro

- Less cold air gets out.

Contra

- Already integrated in fridges?

Notes

030

Cooling Brick

A temporary volume helps keeping the fridge filled so that it can keep its temperature.

Today — 2025 — 2035 — 2045 — 2055 — 2065 **Future**

Address

- Efficiency
- Reduce
- User

Pro

- Less energy is needed when the fridge is empty.

Contra

- Where to store the cooling bricks?
- Inconvenient in implementation.

Notes

031

Sliding Door

A sliding door is enabling the user to reduce the loss of cold air when opening the door.

Today — 2025 — 2035 — 2045 — 2055 — 2065 **Future**

Address

- Efficiency
- Reduce
- User

Pro

- The door is only opened as far as necessary.

Contra

- Possibility of sliding with seals?

Notes

032

Lamella Curtain

A transparent curtain consisting out of lamellas is placed between the door and the interior of a fridge to reduce the loss of cold air when opening the door.

Address

- Efficiency
- Reduce
- User

Pro

- Lamellas prevent loss of cold air.

Contra

- Disturbance in usage.
- Impact?

Notes

033

Order System

Certain food is organized in categories on different tablett / in boxes in the fridge. Example: The breakfast box.

Address

- Efficiency
- Reduce
- User

Pro

- Items can be taken out of the Fridge faster, less loss of cold air.

Contra

- Only usefull for breakfast?
- This order system is not paying attention to the correct storage of different food categories.

Notes

034

Food delivery: Just in Time

Food is ordered and immediately delivered when it is needed. Therefore the possession of a fridge is not needed anymore.

Address

- Sufficiency
- Reduce
- User, Delivery Services

Pro

- Less private fridges.

Contra

- Rebound effect: Food deliveries.

Notes

- (can also be released without drones)

035

"What the fridge?"

A book about the life without a fridge is creating a new movement in society. The fridge is becoming redundant.

Address

- Sufficiency
- Reduce
- User

Pro

- Less personal fridges.
- Greater knowledge of food processing and preservation methods.

Contra

- Such a movement would only reach a small group of society.

Notes

- already exists

036

In-Door-Lighting

The lighting sits in the door and illuminates the interior of the fridge when being opened. All technic parts are in the door.

Today | 2025 | 2035 | 2045 | 2055 | 2065 | **Future**

Address

- Consistency
- Re
- Manufacturer

Pro

- The In-Door-Lighting could be connected to the cooling door.

Contra

- Poorer illumination of the interior.

Notes

037

E-PP

Monomaterial Fridge

The outer shell of the fridge is made out of Expanded Polypropylene (EPP), the inside is made out of Polypropylene (PP). Therefore the fridge consists out of monomaterial.

Today | 2025 | 2035 | 2045 | 2055 | 2065 | **Future**

Address

- Consistency
- Recycle
- Manufacturer, Recycler

Pro

- A monomaterial can be recycled more easy.

Contra

- Practicability?

Notes

038

3D-VIP Panels

3D shaped Vacuum insulation panels with silicic acid are generating a good and filigree fridge insulation.

Address

- Efficiency
- Reduce, Energy Saving
- Manufacturer, Recycler

Pro

- Less energy consumption.

Contra

- Recycling?

Notes

039

Compatible Components

Standards for compatible refrigerator components are introduced, as bases, compressors, seals. This allows an optimal cross-manufacturer usage.

Address

- Consistency
- Remanufacture
- User, Assembler

Pro

-

Contra

-

Notes

040

Fridge with Barcode

A fridge is provided with an individual barcode. The barcode refers to further information as a partlist, materialist etc.. That information supports the user as well as recycler.

Address

- Consistency
- Recycle, Reuse
- Recycler

Pro

- Detailed information supports the Recycler and the user.

Contra

-

Notes

041

Short Term Rental Fridge

A service offering short term rental fridges can be useful for special events as celebrations, visits etc.. This kind of service might reduce the usage of old, additional fridges in peoples cellars.

Address

- Sufficiency
- Reduce
- User

Pro

- Old/inefficient/second fridges can be disposed instead of being kept in the cellar for special events.

Contra

- Enough demand for this kind of service?

Notes

042

Architectural Cold-Heat Solution

Cooled and heated zones in the living environment are architecturally implemented.

Address

- Efficiency
- Reduce
- Architects, Manufacturer

Pro

- Less energy consumption.
- Longer life cycle.

Contra

- High costs and high effort.

Notes

043

3D-printed Parts

Open source data is enabling the user to 3D print replacement parts for the easy to repair fridge.

Address

- Sufficiency
- Reduce
- User

Pro

- Scope of action for the user.

Contra

- Impact?

Notes

044

Energy Efficiency Monitoring

A service could provide information if and when a new and more efficient fridge is needed. People are tending to buy a new fridge even if the old one still works. Educational work could be done here.

Address

- Efficiency
- User

Pro

- Professional support and consulting

Contra

- How much would the user pay for the monitoring service?

Notes

045

Smart Grid

Through a smart grid the fridge is primarily cooling down during the night time, at the day time it keeps its temperature through a cooling storage.

Address

- Efficiency
- User

Pro

- Smart usage of energy.

Contra

- Complexity/smartness of fridge needed.

Notes

046

Energy Efficiency Monitoring

A service could provide information if and when a new and more efficient fridge is needed. People are tending to buy a new fridge even if the old one still works. Educational work could be done here.

Address

- Efficiency
- User

Pro

- Professional support and consulting

Contra

- How much would the user pay for the monitoring service?

Notes

047

Connection to building services

The cooling unit is integrated into the heating and cooling system of the house.

Address

- Efficiency,
- Reduce, Reuse, Recycle,
- Manufacturer, User, architect

Pro

- ...

Contra

- no flexibility

Notes

048

Waste Investment

Thought experiment: What if the material value of consumer goods exceeded the investment value during the period of use?

Address

- Consistency, Sufficiency
- Reduce, Reuse, Recycle, Remanuf...
- Manufacturer, User, Recycler, Trader

Pro

- Consumer goods are handled with care after use. Increasing the chance of reuse and recycling.

Contra

- Consumer goods could be stored as an investment.

Notes Design a product in a way that it can become a good waste investment.(?)

049

Here is room for more ideas

...

Address

- Efficiency, Consistency, Sufficiency
- Reduce, Reuse, Recycle, Remanuf...
- Manufacturer, User, Recycler, Trader, architect

Pro

- ...

Contra

- ...

Notes

050

Anordnung im »U«

Analoge Zukunft - Gewandeltes Jetzt - Technik Zukunft

Neben zahlreichen Ideenkarten ist auch eine Einordnung zwischen zwei Polen erfolgt. Die Ideen konnten zwischen den beiden Polen »Analoge Zukunft« und »Technik-Zukunft« eingeordnet werden. Zur Veranschaulichung kann hier ein Bild dienen, welches vermehrt in der Extremismusforschung anzutreffen ist. Die politische Unterscheidung zwischen Rechts und Links geht auf die verfassungsgebende französische Nationalversammlung im Jahr 1789 zurück (Schwartz and Laponce 1981). Für die Gegenüberstellung dieser beiden Extreme, dessen Pole einerseits weit entfernt, andererseits aber auch nah beieinander sind, gibt es in der Extremismusforschung das Bild des Hufeisens (vgl. Backes, 1989). Wie hilfreich das Bild des Hufeisens in seiner Disziplin wirklich ist, wird kontrovers diskutiert (vgl. Forum für kritische Rechtsextremismusforschung, 2011). Ebenso lässt sich die Einsortierung zwischen die Pole Links und Rechts infrage stellen und erweitern, wie es Bruno Latour in das terrestrische Manifest fordert (Latour, 2018).

In diesem Gestaltungskontext scheint das Hufeisen hingegen ein angemessenes Mittel, um die vorhandenen Ideenrichtungen einzuordnen.

Die Idee einer analogen und die einer technischen Zukunft sind grundlegend verschieden, haben aber eines gemein: Konsequenter verfolgt machen sie ein Leben ohne privates Kühlgerät (wieder) vorstellbar. Die breite Masse der Ideen befindet sich vorwiegend in der Mitte des Bogens und kann unter dem Begriff »gewandeltes jetzt« subsumiert werden. Die verschiedenen konzeptuellen Zugrichtungen schließen sich nicht aus. Vielmehr entstehen hier parallel vorstellbare Zukünfte. Während manche ihr Ziel darin sehen, Dinge ohne künstliche Kälte verzehrbar zu halten, wird es andere geben, die ihren lokalen Essens-Speicher am liebsten aufgeben und sich aus der »Cloud« zu ernähren, vorausgesetzt sie sind an ein schnelles »Lebensmittelnetz« angeschlossen. Die Auseinandersetzung mit den extremen Ideen ergänzt die Konzepte, die zahlreich in der Mitte um das »gewandelte jetzt« entstehen.

Analoge
Zukunft

Technik
Zukunft

Gewandeltes
Jetzt

002: Anordnung der Ideen mittels »U«

"What the fridge?"
A book about the life without a fridge is creating a new movement in society. The fridge is becoming redundant.

Earth Refrigerator
An earth refrigerator is used to keep groceries cool without needing any power supply.

Window Sill Cooling
An evaporative refrigerator for the window sill, not much bigger than a filter pot, actually keeps the essential food in the household fresh.

Solar Fridge
The fridge is being powered by solar energy when it is possible.

Community Fridge
Commonly used fridges in residential buildings can facilitate cooling space for more than just one household.

Low-Tech Fridge Extension
The actual fridge volume can be temporarily extended by the usage of an additional storage module, which is cooled by low-tech cool packs. Therefore the actual fridge size could be reduced.

Planted Fridge
An evaporative refrigerator for the balcony is equipped with planting on top. Through watering the plants the fridge is getting the rest water which is used for evaporation and cooling.

Utilization of Residual Heat
The heat that derives through the food of the fridge is being reused.

Exterior Cooling
Outdoor temperatures are being used to cool groceries. Cooling can be restricted to the inside of the fridge to reduce the energy usage. Also there might be outside storage systems that are enabling the food storage on the balcony / garden.

Foodsharing Fridge
Community fridges are placed in neighbourhoods especially for food sharing reasons.

House Insulation
The insulation layer is added to the outer fridge shell, similar to the process of insulating a house.

A Central Food Storage
The fridge is the central food storage of the household and is enabling appropriate storage space for all groceries - cooled and not cooled.

Monomaterial Fridge
The outer shell of the fridge is made out of Expanded Polystyrene (EPS). The inside is made out of Polypropylene (PP). Therefore the fridge consists out of monomaterial.

Cooling Brick
A temporary volume helps keeping the fridge fresh so that it can keep its temperature.

Alternative Isolation Materials
Alternative and natural materials such as for example fungus are being used as an isolation. These materials need to be eco-friendly or recyclable.

Modular Technology
The technological part of the fridge is modular and therefore it can be easily repaired, it can be upgraded or exchanged.

In-Door-Lighting
The lighting sits in the door and illuminates the interior of the fridge when being opened.

Cooling Door
The refrigerator is reduced to its door. Therefore this cooling technology is inside of a door and can be mounted on an installed box or a wall niche.

Recycling Fridge
This fridge is consisting at least out of 40% of recycling materials. Furthermore recycling of the fridge components at the end of its lifetime is made possible.

Order System
Certain food is organized in categories on different shelves / or boxes in the fridge. Example: The breakfast box.

Directional Fridge
The fridge has a clear direction to enable the extraction of the coolant more easy.

Fridge with Barcode
A fridge is provided with an individual barcode. The barcode refers to further information as a product, materials etc. That information supports the user as well as recycle.

003: Einordnung der Ideenkarten zwischen zwei Polen

Food delivery: Just in Time
Food is ordered and immediately delivered where it is needed. Therefore the possession of a fridge is not needed anymore.

Life without Fridge
Cooled food delivery hubs are available in neighbourhoods. Purchasing behavior of people has changed. Regularly fresh food deliveries can be picked up at the hub. The shopping experience at a supermarket is getting redundant.

Panel Construction
The outer shell of the fridge is constructed out of modular metal sheet material.

Clever Connector
A clever connector is used to join the exterior of the fridge. This can be combined with modular exterior panels. Therefore the fridge can be disassembled more easily.

Modular Exterior
The exterior appearance and arrangement of the fridge is modular. If the design is not fitting anymore it can be easily adjusted to the new preferences of the user.

Fridge with a Handle
A fridge with an integrated handle can make the transport, return to and handling at the recycler's refurbishment company more easy.

Rent a Fridge
A rental fridge is a solution for people, whose living conditions are often in a state of change. In each living situation the right cooling unit could be provided.

Cool Chain Delivery
Delivery services are able to deliver food directly into the customers' refrigerator. The domestic fridge freezer combination is accessible for the supplier.

Architectural Cold-Heat Solution
Cooled and heated zones in the living environment are architecturally implemented.

Transparency of the Inside
A transparent order system in the inside of the fridge doors, visual labeling etc. can support a more efficient usage of the cooling volume and can prevent from long searches for specific items.

Compatible Components
Standards for compatible refrigerant components are introduced, as bases, compressors, coils. This allows an optimal cross-manufacturer usage.

Fridge Disposal
A deposit is paid when a refrigerator is purchased. It is paid back when the appliance is returned correctly.

Short Term Rental Fridge
A service offering short term rental fridges can be useful for special events in collaborative, public etc. This kind of service might reduce the usage of old additional fridges in peoples' offices.

Connected Cooling
A large refrigerator is more efficient than two small ones. In this concept, one large refrigerator is used across two apartments. A wall break-through between apartments would be conceivable here.

Transparency of the Outside
A transparent appearance is enabling transparency in the usage. The door can locate needed items before opening the door, to reduce the cooling loss. Furthermore food waste might be reduced as the fridge content is more present.

Multiple Openings
Smaller and more fridge opening possibilities (doors, drawers etc.) are enabling less cooling loss when opened.

Lamella Curtain
A transparent curtain consisting out of lamellas is placed between the door and the interior of a fridge to reduce the loss of cold air when opening the door.

Renewable Film in the Inner Wall
After a period of usage, the fridge interior is equipped with a new film.

Smart Grid
Through a smart grid the fridge is primarily cooling down during the night time, at the day time it keeps its temperature through a cooling storage, to repair fridge.

3D-printed Parts
Open source data is enabling the user to 3D print replacement parts for the easy to repair fridge.

Door Closing/Opening
The fridge door is closing automatically after being opened to prevent it from being left open. Furthermore the resistance of the opening of the door can be reconsidered.

Sliding Door
A sliding door is enabling the user to reduce the loss of cold air when opening the door.

Energy Efficiency Monitoring
A service could provide information if cool down is more and more efficient. Fridge is needed. People are handling to use a new fridge even if the old one still works. Educational work could be done here.

Bewertung der Einzelideen

Die gesammelten Ideen wurden auf Grundlage des Nachhaltigkeitsradars vor der weiteren Ausarbeitung bewertet.

In Anlehnung an den Nachhaltigkeitsradar aus dem Transition Design Guide (Liedtke, Köhlert, Huber & Baedeker, 2019 S. 59) haben Projektmitarbeitende des Helmholtz Instituts, des Wuppertal Instituts und der Folkwang Universität der Künste die Ideen bewertet. Auffallend ist hier, dass Methoden wie eine Ressourcenintensitätsanalyse oder eine Lebenszyklusanalyse viel zu ausufernd wären, um eine Bewertung in diesem Stadium der Gestaltung durchzuführen. Der Aufwand einer Bewertung stünde in einem sehr ungleichen Verhältnis zum Bewertungsgegenstand. Verlockend ist es, dem Impuls zu folgen, weiter zu gestalten, bis die Idee so weit ausgereift ist, dass sich der Aufwand einer fundierten Bewertung zu lohnen scheint. Mit einer Adaption des Nachhaltigkeitsradars ist ein Bewertungstool gewählt, das den noch unpräzisen Ideen gerecht werden kann. Mit den Indikatoren: Lebensmittelkonservierung, Energieeffizi-

enz in der Nutzung, Nutzungsdauer, Reparierbarkeit/ Wiedernutzung, Sammelquote/Transport, Rückgewinnungsraten, ökologisch, sozial, ökonomisch/ Umsetzbarkeit, Ressourcen-Nutzen Verhältnis und Rebound Gefahr hat eine Bewertung stattgefunden. In den Indikatoren taucht auch der Punkt „Wunschkonzert“ auf, dies dient zum offensichtlichen „Schummeln“ z. B. wenn die Idee aus einem Grund besser erscheint, als sie dasteht. Durch das Sichtbarmachen und Vergleichen der persönlichen Bewertung lassen sich einige Ideen als abwegig für das Projektziel identifizieren, andere Ideen erfahren bei allen Zustimmung auf bestimmten Ebenen. Bei einigen Ideen stellt sich, durch stark abweichende Bewertungen heraus, dass hier der Interpretationsspielraum noch sehr hoch ist.

004: Bewertungsschema in Anlehnung an den Nachhaltigkeitsradar

Bewertungstabelle

Einblick in den Prozess

005: Bewertungstabelle der ersten Ideenkarte (bewertet von CT)

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